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MULTI-INTER-TRANS DISCIPLINARY RESEARCH TOWARDS MANAGEMENT AND COMMERCE

Multi and inter disciplinary research are often used interchangeably but originally they referred to different approaches. When experts from different fields work together on a common subject within the boundaries of their own discipline, they are said to adopt a multidisciplinary approach. However, if they stick to these boundaries they may reach a point where the project cannot progress any further. They will then have to bring themselves to the fringes of their own fields to form new concepts and ideas--and create a whole new, interdisciplinary field. A trans disciplinary team is an interdisciplinary team whose members have developed sufficient trust and mutual confidence to rise above or go beyond the normal limits of disciplinary boundaries and adopt a more holistic approach.

So is multi- (or inter- or trans-) disciplinarily today's hottest buzzword in management careers ,well judging by the numerous conferences and training programmes around the world, it certainly looks like it, Transforming Undergraduate Education for Future Research Management" that was requested by the Commerce and Management Institute. It strongly recommended that undergraduate education should incorporate management and commerce , accounting & finance, business research, consumer behavior & relationship management. corporate governance, economics, e-commerce, entrepreneurship, human resources, management, information technology, business, law, supply chain management, marketing communication, marketing, management, selling and marketing techniques, strategic management, total quality management, tax management, risk management,training and development until "interdisciplinary thinking and work become second nature." to think about the opportunities waiting for them at the interface with the management and commerce.

Multidisciplinary has a lot to offer to early-career scientists in terms of opportunities and excitement. The Human Genome Project, the World Wide Web, and the boundaries of the infinitely small are only a few of the fertile fields where new research is flourishing. Those scientists who have taken the plunge swear by multidisciplinary and will even say that you won't be able to survive in science if you don't keep an open mind to the advantages afforded by multidisciplinary approaches. But if the rewards are great, so too are the challenges. Understanding the concepts underlying a discipline other than your own, finding a common language to communicate ideas, trusting research you haven't the skills to assess yourself, and finding somewhere to publish are only a few of them.

We have gathered in this feature articles that offer you snapshots of multidisciplinary research in different countries, insight into what can be gained with such an approach and what it takes to become multidisciplinary, and a sample of the programmes and centers that can help you on your journey.